

SCHOOL-HOME ROLES: AN EXPLORATION TOWARDS PUPILS' STUDY HABITS

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School-Home Roles: An Exploration towards Pupils' Study Habits

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Abstract

The study attempted to determine the extent of school-home roles in terms of parenting, school-home communication, and parents' participation in school activities; and the pupils' study habits as well as the significant relationship between the school-home roles and pupils' study habits. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized, and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, frequency count, standard deviation, percentages to analyze the extent of school-home roles and pupils' study habits; Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the school-home roles and pupils' study habits. Findings revealed that parenting has no direct relationship to pupils' study habits while school-home communication and parents' participation in school activities indicate low or slight relationships to pupils' learning habits. Subsequently, it was recommended that in order to intensify pupils' study habits, teachers provide a supportive environment that promotes development of pupils' study habits.

Keywords: *pupils' study habits, parenting, parents' participation in school activities, school-home communication, school-home roles*

Introduction

The 21st -century learning has regenerated the role of parents from being mere supporters to being active associates in their child's learning. This century is marked by quality and speedy change and parenting needs to respond consequently. One thing that will never change is that parents are their child's first and most essential teachers.

The National Education Policy Act 27 of 1996 stresses parental choices and responsibilities and strategies have been developed to encourage parental participation of home and school and to link home and school more effectively. However, little knowledge exists regarding the part that the children play in the process of parental involvement in education, although it is the duty of the educators to equip learners with the strategies to involve their parents.

Theory of Vygotsky which is "zone of proximal development" emphasizes on parents as partners in their child's life and child's education are crucial as he believed that everything a child learns is through the interactions with "knowledgeable partners" (Brooks, 2011). As we know, a child spends most of their time with their parent(s) during their early development, therefore emphasizing the importance of modeling positive behavior for the child.

The parent role is important to understand since it is through this role that individuals perceive what parenting involves and consequently parent children. At various points on any given day, individuals perform other social roles, such as being a friend, teacher or learner, employer, or employee. But when individuals interact with their children, they are performing the role of being a parent. Therefore, the Parent Developmental Theory defines who parents are, examines the parent role individual's play, clarifies how parents and parenting develop and change over time, and explains how the parent role relates to parenting activities.

It is important to consider the study habits of the pupils on how they manage their time efficiently, and how to have effective varied study techniques to keep them afloat. These things are important for them to form good study habits. These things are important in order to understand how these pupils respond to the demands of acquiring good grades as expected by parents and school authorities. In such the cooperation of the parents and teachers is needed because they are going to take another step-in learning process which is the secondary level or high school. In addition to that, high school is the training ground for college. If pupils started poor study habit, they will probably have a hard time to cope up in college.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine and analyze the correlation between the home-school roles and the Grade 3 pupils' study habits of North 3 District, Division of Gingoog City, school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the extent of school-home roles when grouped according to:
 - 1.1. parenting;
 - 1.2. school-home communication; and
 - 1.3. parents' participation in school activities?
2. What are the study habits of the respondents in terms of frequency of study, time to study, and duration for study.
3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' study habits and the school-home roles when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. parenting;
 - 3.2. school-home communication; and

3.3. parents' participation in school activities?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive correlational-design which is appropriate for its objective in determining the school-home roles and the pupils' study habits. The data gathered by the study provided the basis of inference on parents' profile as a factor influencing pupils study habits.

The method involved description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of prevailing conditions. The investigation on the respondents' profile on study habits and their respective academic performance served to focus on this study.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the 90 Grade 3 learners in Gingoog City North 3 District's selected schools. The accessibility, location, and size of these schools are taken into consideration. The respondents are the ninety (90) Grade 3 pupils from the four schools which is the total populations of Grade 3 from four schools. The respondents are chosen as the sample respondents of the study.

Instrument

This study adapted the research of Laurilla (2017) entitled, "Impact of Parental Roles to the Academic Performance in Pupils".

There are two sets of research instruments used for the purpose of gathering information needed for the study. The first set inquired about the Epstein's Joyce framework on school-home roles namely, 5-item for parenting, 5-item for school-home communication, and 5-item for parents' participation in school. The second set refers to the pupils' study habits, namely, frequency to study, time to study, and duration to study.

Procedure

A letter of approval from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Gingoog City was sought before conducting the research indicating permission to conduct the study.

After the superintendent granted the request, the letter was to the principal of the four (4) schools in North 3 District, Division of Gingoog City, namely, Sagu-Ilaw Ta Kabuka Elementary School, Bayawon Ta Malagwas Elementary School, Kalipay Central School, and Sangalan Integrated School.

The administration and data-gathering were done in a polite manner to avoid suspicion that might crop up in the future and all the data were kept confidential.

Data Analysis

To get the analysis and interpretation of the study the following statistical measures are employed:

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used in Problem 1.

Mean and Standard Deviation were utilized for problem 2.

Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was used for the significant relationship between the pupils' study habits and the school-home roles.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on school-home roles: an exploration towards pupils' study habits. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem 1. What is the extent of school-home roles when grouped according to, Parenting, School-home communication, and Parents' participation in school activities?

Homes like school can help pupils to learn by providing the needed material environment that is organized in a way that it can be easily assimilated into the learner's cognitive development. School-home roles promote study habit and strengthened learning performance especially when parents are engaged in their children's education.

Research revealed that parents provide the major influence in their children's education from birth through adolescence. They guide in the development of their character and mental health which help form the foundation from which their children develop lifelong attitudes and interests.

Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution of school-home roles when grouped according to parenting.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of School-Home Roles in terms of Parenting

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Parents provide all the needs so child could study well.	3.38	1.01	Always
2. Parents praise children for outstanding achievements in school.	3.18	1.0	Oftentimes
3. Parents are willing to pay for projects in school.	3.28	.994	Always
4. Parents educate their child to be respectful to teachers and classmates in school.	3.51	.851	Always
5. Parents are concerned that their child is in company of good people.	3.11	1.05	Oftentimes
Overall Mean	3.29	.981	Always

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/2.50-3.24 Oftentimes/1.75-2.49/Sometimes/1.00-1.74 Never

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of school-home roles in terms of parenting. Overall, the respondents rated parenting as “Always” with a mean of 3.29 (SD=.981). This result indicates that parents always provide their children’s schooling needs, willing to support school projects, and taught children to be respectful to teachers and fellow learners. Parents play an important role in their child’s academic and educational development and take the essential support in optimizing learning at home and at school.

Cogan, et al (2021) pointed out that parents play an indispensable role in home-school learning as they help develop their child’s study habits and improve as well as maximize learning through home and school academic and educational supports.

The indicator “parents educate child to be respectful to teachers and fellow learners” obtained the highest mean value of 3.51 (SD=.851) which is verbally described as “always” which indicates that parents are constantly educate their children to respect teachers and their fellow learners in school and at the same time to exercise greater reverence and astonishments on their teachers and classmates.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.11 (SD=1.06) is verbally described as “Oftentimes” in the indicator “Parents are concerned that their child is in company of good people”. The result implies that parents normally are concerned about the type of people their children are in contact with and they accompany with in school.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of School-Home Roles in terms of School-Home Communication

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Parents attend Homeroom PTA meeting regularly (every grading period)	3.29	.877	Always
2. Parents coordinate with teachers on the issues and concerns in their child’s studies.	3.00	.861	Oftentimes
3. Parents asks their child what they can do to improve their grades.	2.91	1.242	Oftentimes
4. Parents visit the school to check if the environment is conducive for learning.	2.65	1.153	Oftentimes
5. Parents communicate with teachers regularly for updates in school and child’s performance.	2.62	1.076	Oftentimes
Overall Mean	2.89	1.042	Oftentimes

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/2.50-3.24 Oftentimes/1.75-2.49/Sometimes/1.00-1.74 Never

Table 1.2 presents the mean distribution of school-home roles in terms of school-home communication. Overall, the respondents rated school-home communication as “Oftentimes” practiced and observed with a mean of 2.89 (SD=1.042). This result indicates that parents and teachers developed and maintained an open communication to discuss pupils’ school activities and improve learning performance.

Green-Hennessy (2022) averred that school-home communication is an important way for parents and teachers to keep each other informed about the child’s academic progress and learning needs.

The indicator “parents attend homeroom PTA meeting regularly (every grading period)” obtained the highest mean value of 3.29 (SD=.877) which is verbally described as “always” which indicates that parents are interested to take part in school activities thus they are motivated to attend and participate in homeroom meetings and consultations.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.62 (SD=1.076) is verbally described as “oftentimes” in the indicator “parents communicate with teachers regularly for updates in school and child’s performance”. The result implies that parents updated with the school activities and their child’s performance through forging regular communication with the class advisers.

Salazar, et al (2022) affirmed school-home communication facilitates learning and understanding between educators and students. It builds strong relationships and trust, fostering a positive learning environment. Home-school communication allows for individualized support and differentiation, catering to diverse learners’ needs.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of School-Home Roles in terms of Parents’ Participation in School Activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Parents give full support for the clean-up drive in school.	3.05	1.105	Oftentimes
2. Parents attend orientation on drugs in school	3.07	1.10	Oftentimes
3. Parents actively participate in school maintenance program.	3.22	.884	Oftentimes
4. Parents donate educational resources to help improve instructional delivery	2.14	1.259	Sometimes
5. Parents participate in school activities such as nutrition month, Brigada Eskwela, and the like	2.92	.926	Oftentimes
Overall Mean	2.88	1.054	Oftentimes

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/2.50-3.24 Oftentimes/1.75-2.49/Sometimes/1.00-1.74 Never

Table 1.3 presents the mean distribution of school-home roles in terms of parents' participation in school activities. Overall, the respondents rated parents' participation in school activities as "Oftentimes" observed with a mean of 2.88 (SD=1.054). This result indicates that parents actively involved in school activities such as Brigada Eskwela as yearly clean-up drive and school preparation for class opening, meetings and conferences of parents-teachers-association, nutrition month celebration, and the like.

Bartolome, et al (2023) asserted that parents' participation in school activities as well as the education of their children has been found out to produce positive outcomes in many aspects including increased pupils' attendance and satisfaction with school, better academic achievement, motivation, school attachment, responsibility and confidence, better social adaptation and less discipline problems.

The indicator "parents actively participate in school maintenance program" obtained the highest mean value of 3.22 (SD=.884) which is verbally described "oftentimes" which indicates that parents were actively involved and participated in school maintenance programs such as Brigada Eskwela or the cleaning-up program for the preparation of school for the coming school year, meetings and conferences, Parent-teacher association, and the like.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.14 (SD=1.259) is verbally described as "sometimes" in the indicator "parents donate educational resources to help improve instructional delivery". The result implies that parents only occasionally contribute and donate educational materials or resources to help teachers improve teaching or instructional service.

Salazar, et al (2022) avowed that parents' support in academic and school activities such as participation in the school maintenance programs such as Brigada Eskwela and parent-teacher association as well as on its endowment for school projects forged strong collaboration and partnership which help inspire and motivate pupils to develop school and academic engagements.

Problem 2. What is the study habits of the respondents in terms of frequency of study, time to study, and duration for study?

Pupils' academic success through learning performance is predictive of pupils' study habits. Study habits can be based on the frequency of study, time of study, and duration for study.

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of pupils' study habits in terms of frequency of study, time of study, and duration for study.

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Study Habits

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualifying Description</i>
1.	Study lesson every day.	3.31	.944	Always
2.	Study only when there is examination.	2.59	1.226	Sometimes
3.	Spend 30 minutes to one hour studying a lesson	2.71	1.124	Sometimes
4.	Study once in every grading period.	2.82	.966	Sometimes
5.	Study when failed the exam or quiz.	2.46	.1.247	Sometimes
6.	Set schedule for study and lesson review.	2.25	1.259	Seldom
7.	Consider and conscious of the time of the day to study.	2.10	1.151	Seldom
8.	Study only when feel like to study.	2.03	1.064	Seldom
9.	Prefer to study in quiet and inaudible place.	2.05	1.164	Seldom
10.	Spend much time in one subject and not enough on others.	2.02	1.060	Seldom
	Overall Mean	2.188	1.121	Seldom

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Always/2.50-3.24 Sometimes/1.75-2.49/Seldom/1.00-1.74 Never

Table 2.1 presents the mean distribution of pupils' study habits. Overall, the respondents rated pupils' study habits as "seldom" practiced with a mean of 2.188 (SD=1.121). This result indicates that pupils infrequently or rarely practice effective study habits. It can be deduced based on findings that infrequent practice of good study habits minimally helps pupils to stay on top in their tasks and balance their studying with everything they need to do. Pupils can also help others to study more efficiently, so they can make the most of their study time.

However, Bartolome, et al (2023) emphasized that developing study habits can increase pupils' confidence, competence, and self-esteem. Study habits can also reduce anxiety about tests and deadlines in academic subjects. Additionally, pupils' study habits lead to better academic performance, increased knowledge retention, and improved time management skills.

The indicator "study lesson every day" obtained the highest mean value of 3.31 (SD.944) which is verbally described as "always" which indicates that pupils study their lessons continuously and regularly.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.02 (SD=1.060) in the indicator "spend much time in one subject and not enough on others" is verbally described as "seldom".

The result implies that pupils occasionally or rarely spend time studying in one subject and setting aside other subjects which suggests that they were able to spend time correspondingly in all their subjects.

Castillo, et al (2023) averred that pupils need to develop and use active study habits in order to make learning more beneficial and use their own habitual tendencies and practices that they depict during the process of gaining information through the varieties of activities such as time management, setting an appropriate study environment, appropriate note-taking strategies, and choosing main ideas, and organization.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between respondents' study habits and the school-home roles when grouped according to: Parenting, School-Home Communication, and Parents' Participation in School Activities?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the pupils' study habits and school-home roles in terms of parenting, school-home communication, and parents' participation in school activities.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between Pupils' Study Habits and School-Home Roles*

School-Home Roles	Pupils' Study Habits			
	(r)	Probability Value Sig. (2 tailed)	Interpretation	Decision on H ₀₁
Parenting	.010	.925	No linear relationship	Accepted
School-Home Communication	.155	.145	Indicates low or slight relationship	Rejected
Parents' Participation in School Activities	.301	.004	Indicates low or slight relationship	Rejected

*Significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' study habits and school-home roles. Results revealed that pupils' study habits denote "No Linear Relationship" to parenting ($r=.010$) as indicated in the probability value of .925. This result indicates that pupils' study habits were not influenced by school-home roles in terms of parenting.

The findings imply that the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between pupils' study habits and school-home roles in terms of parenting is hereby "accepted" because pupils' study habits and parenting had no significant relationship.

It can be inferred based on findings that pupils' study habits can be attributed to other factors other than parenting. Castillo, et al (2023) asserted that pupils' study habits can be developed through the conduct of distinguished study techniques which help improve the psychological and mental readiness of pupils to study their lessons.

Moreover, results recommended that pupils' study habits indicate low or slight relationship to school-home communication ($r=.155$) as indicated in probability value of .145. This result implies that pupils' study habits are insignificantly predictive of the school-home communication. It can be inferred that pupils' study habits are negligibly influenced by school-home roles in terms of school-home communication. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between pupils' study habits and school-home roles in terms of school-home communication is hereby "rejected" because it was found that pupils' study habit and school-home communication had slight relationship.

Additionally, it was also revealed on findings that pupils' study habits indicate low or slight relationship to school-home roles in terms of parents' participation to school activities ($r=.301$) as indicated in the probability value of .004. This result implies that school-home roles in terms of parents' participation in school activities negligibly influenced pupils' study habits. Henceforth, this study indicated that the null hypothesis is "rejected" because it was found that pupils' study habit and parents' participation in school activities had slight relationship.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

School-home roles in terms of parenting, school-home communication, and parents' participation in school activities are factors believed to influence pupils' study habits. Parents' role in the education of their children is highly recognized because the primary motivation for the child learning and study habits should start at home with the parents as the first teachers. Additionally, parents' ability to maintain an open communication with teachers and their participation in school activities help them be aware of their child's academic and school performance as well as the school behaviors of the school children.

Pupils' study habits are composite of trainings and pupils' personal motivation to learn and considered as the most important predictors of pupils' academic performance. Pupils must learn and apply study skills to organize and learn a large amount of information.

Parents had greater influence in the development of their child's study habits. They played direct control and supervision of their child's learning development. However, studies under review revealed that parenting has no direct relationship to pupils' study habits formation because it is presumably argued that pupils develop their study habits in school with teachers who have encouraged them to read and study.

School-home communication and parents' participation in school activities encouraged pupils to take their studies more seriously. Information on their school performance can easily be communicated between parents and teachers and parents' continued participation in school activities intensified pupils' motivation to improve classroom engagements in learning activities because of the greater understanding that parents' support inspired learners to advance learning.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will be provided with information on the influence of school-home roles to pupils' study habits in order to provide the needed technical support and instructional intervention be initiated as part of its policy implementation.

School Principals/School Heads are recommended to provide support to teachers to develop their personal commitment to come up with authentic study habits strategies which help promote pupils' academic competence and performance.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously develop and enhance their skills in helping pupils enhance their study habits and at the same time provide supportive environment that promotes development of pupils' study habits.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and ensure that their children are provided with appropriate support in enhancing their study habits to improve class and school performance.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization of information and communication technology resources which help support pupils' study habits and learning effectiveness.

Future Researchers are encouraged to conduct a similar study on the study habits strategies of teachers and pupils' learning performance in order to investigate further the interrelationship of each variable as well as to identify mitigating variables that help influence the development of pupils' study habits and learning performance.

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